

ASSESSING THE INFLUENCE OF OIL INCOME ON HUMAN DEVELOPMENT OUTCOMES IN NIGERIA (2005–2023)

Nwoye Chukwudi Emmanuel

Department of Accountancy, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19912806>

ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>The study examined the impact of petroleum income on human development index in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to find out the impact of crude oil export income on human development index in Nigeria, to determine the impact petroleum profit tax on human development index in Nigeria, to evaluate the impact of royalty's income on human development index in Nigeria. The study adopted ex post facto research design. The study data were sourced from Central Bank Statistical Bulletin and World Development Indicator. The stated hypotheses were analyzed using descriptive statistics, unit root test and multiple regression. The findings of this study revealed that: crude oil export income has a positive but statistically non-significant effect on human development in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.0299$, $p = 0.1515$); petroleum profit tax exerts a negative and significant effect on human development ($\beta = 0.0738$, $p = 0.0399$); royalty's income has a negative and significant effect on human development in Nigeria ($\beta = -0.0548$, $p = 0.0000$). In conclusion, petroleum income, while economically substantial, does not guarantee developmental outcomes in contexts where governance and resource allocation frameworks may be weak or misaligned with developmental goals. It was recommended that the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC) should establish a mandatory development fund sourced from royalty payments. This fund should be transparently managed and strictly allocated to human development priorities in oil-producing communities, including healthcare delivery, educational support, and livelihood enhancement programs.</p>	<p>Petroleum Income, Human Development Index, Crude Oil Export Income, Human Development Index</p>

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Every government all over the world exist to provide basic social amenities and infrastructural needs of her citizens through adequate provision of basic healthcare, food security, educational development and promotion

of better leaving standard that capture the three elements of Human development index as proposed by UNDP 1990. The human development index generally known as HDI is a statistical tool used to measure a country's overall achievement in its social and economic dimensions. The measurement of human development index is an aggregation of three central index of a country's social and economic development. These basic necessities of life are made possible to satisfy the needs and welfare of citizenry from government revenue sources, both oil and nonoil.

Nigeria, often regarded as the giant of Africa, was once the continent's leading crude oil producer and ranked 9th among global petroleum exporters, but due to market volatility and falling oil prices, it currently holds the 11th position (Nnah, 2023). The discovery of natural resources in Nigeria in form of black gold or the goose that lay the golden eggs as being referred to in Niger Delta region where oil and gas sector activities thrive has open more window of opportunities to other sectors of the economy. The petroleum sector is categorized into main three layers according to chain of oil and gas distribution as upstream, downstream and midstream operations in Nigeria with various classifications and large number of regulatory players participating to the entire value chain with over 80% crude oil production in upstream activities produced by international oil giant like Chevron, Shell, Mobil, Addax, Agip and Total E&P.). International oil companies control more than 90% of oil reserves, however, marginal field players have increased production by 15% yearly over the previous ten years, whilst production by International Oil Companies IOCs has decreased by 4% annually on average (Babayomi, 2023). Over the years, Petroleum revenue has been the major driver of Nigeria's economy, contributing 33% of the GDP, 76% of government revenue, and 95% of foreign exchange earnings (NBS 2023). Consequently, government has continued to exercise control and ownership over the nation's petroleum operations, with the Petroleum Industry Act of 2021 signed into law being the most recent operational act.

Oil and gas income otherwise known as petroleum income could be classified as major revenue from sale of crude oil proceeds oil rent or concessional rights, PPT and Royalties income that go into federation account as a result of exploration, exploitation and production activities, arguably has led to the development of other sectors of the economy for improvement of human lives, educational and infrastructural funding from the revenues accruing from oil and gas sectors. All monetary sums received by a government from petroleum sources are referred to as revenue. Under the PPT establishment act of 1959, Finance act of 2023, classified Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) as a tax or levy imposed on the companies' earnings (profit) from petroleum activities under the Nigerian Petroleum Income Tax Act. It is imposed, assessed and payable on the companies' profits for their engagement in petroleum operations during any accounting period, usually one year of about 85% for upstream activities.

Other related petroleum income include; rents, royalties, margins and profit-sharing elements associated with oil mining, prospecting and exploration leases. Oil rent, oil pipeline and license fees, signature bonuses penalty from gas flared, Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPCL) earnings from direct sales, proceeds from local sales of crude oil to NNPCL, proceeds from export sales of crude oil and gas etc. Moreover, crude oil sales entail the sale of crude to the domestic and international refineries; whereas, the licensing fees or concessional rights are fees paid to the government for issuing different types of licenses for crude oil prospecting, exploration and exploitation granted by the government under Section 2(1) (a) of the Nigerian Petroleum Act (Ebimobowei, 2022). Undoubtedly, the Petroleum Industry Act (PIA, 2021) and Global Memorandum of Understanding (GMOU) by international oil companies have come to stay such as Dangote Refineries in Lagos and other modular refineries by Federal Government of Nigeria to streamline the participation of other player into petroleum sectors

and deregulation policy of the government aim at stimulating and growing other sectors of the economy for improvement of human lives.

Discovery of crude oil and oil boom of 1970 has created Dutch disease syndrome in Nigeria economy and the neglect of other sectors of economy like agriculture which was formally the mainstay of Nigerian economy. The boom in oil sector further created a high poverty index, resulting from the decay in infrastructural development in Niger Delta Region and Nigeria in general. Huge revenue generated from oil and gas sector since the past five decades are yet to be translated into a meaningful development. However, issues of lingering poverty, neglect of our health institutions, lack of power, energy, road, transportation, are all deteriorating. Crude oil discovery has had certain impacts on the Nigeria economy both positively and negatively. On the negative side, this can be considered with respect to the surrounding communities within which the oil wells are exploited. Some of these communities still suffer environmental degradation, which leads to deprivation of means of livelihood and other economic and social amenities.

The discovery of large crude deposits in Nigeria has not resulted to improvement living standard which could be attributed to inefficiency, corruption, poor turn around maintenance, monopoly powers, bureaucracy, sabotage and rising level of poverty, low per capital income and poor infrastructural development, subsidy policy and the sector has been declining contrary to expectations (Umenweke & Chukwuma, 2023). Hence, the reduction in demand for crude in international market and OPEC regulatory policy framework forces its price to fall and in turn reducing total oil revenue accruable to the government. Besides oil price fluctuation that affect the revenue earning of the Nigerian government, it is alleged that corrupt practices in the oil sector like looting and embezzlement of the revenues generated from crude oil, illegal diversion of crude oil and crude oil theft, strikes, wars and decline in global demand for oil, vandalization of pipeline, illicit export of crude oil and militancy in the upstream sector against oil companies, among others, have militated against the equitable distribution of benefit of oil revenue to the country's populace. Poor tax planning efforts by corporations (including MNCs) have brought about revenue losses to developing countries like Nigeria. In 2022, the Federal Inland Revenue Service reported that companies' income tax contributed only 24 percent of total tax revenue to the government coffers (NBS, 2023).

Scholarly works had been carried on petroleum income contribution basically on economic growth and development such as Omesi and Berembo (2020) result showed that oil revenue has a negative but significant relationship with human development index, the negative contribution arose as a result of the resource curse ideology. Oladipo Nkamnebe, Nwokocha and Sani,(2023) revealed a negative impact between federal independent revenue (FIR) and economic growth in Nigeria, Okonkwo and Madueke (2016) revealed that oil revenues have an insignificant effect on economic development of a country both in the short and long run and further reported a no causal relationship between oil revenue and the economic development of Nigeria. The obvious question that follows from this is; “why” would a country so abundantly blessed with oil and other natural resources still be classified as „developing“ after five decades of independence? Additionally, none of the prior studies has empirically investigated petroleum revenue impact and human development indices in Nigeria from 2005 to 2024 with modifications and changes in finance act of 2023 and related amendment of PIA, 2021. In order to close this existing gap and expand the frontier of knowledge in this area of study, this research work is consummated by investigating the impact of petroleum revenue on HDI in Nigeria using the three indicators of measurement which are healthy life, knowledge and education, and suitable living standard. The study therefore seems to be more robust, current and relevant for policy making.

1.1 Objective of the Study

The main Objective of this study is to examine the impact of petroleum income on Human Development Index in Nigeria. The specific objectives include:

- (i) To find out the impact of crude oil export income on Human Development index in Nigeria.
- (ii) To determine the impact Petroleum Profit Tax on Human Development index in Nigeria.
- (iii) To evaluate the impact of Royalties income on Human Development index in Nigeria

1.2 Research Hypotheses

The hypotheses of the study were raised based on the objectives and research questions to guide the study in a null form.

H0₁: Crude oil export income has no significant impact on Human Development Index in Nigeria.

H0₂: Petroleum profit tax has no significant impact on Human Development Index in Nigeria.

H0₃: Royalties Income has no significant impact on human development index in Nigeria.

2.0 REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE 2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Petroleum Income

Major revenue sources of Nigerian government are oil and nonoil revenue. Most petroleum revenue of the government come from natural resources deposit from downstream and upstream activities. The petroleum income referred to as oil and gas revenue earned from the sales of petroleum products by any company or organization engaged in petroleum operations (Akintayo, 2022). Petroleum products or crude oil is a nonrenewable resource, implying that it can't be substituted naturally at the rate it is consumed. Income from petroleum resources include Petroleum profit tax, oil rent otherwise known as concession rights or licenses fees, royalties, crude oil sales. Hence, domestic and international crude oil sales revenue attract foreign direct investment and foreign exchange erring to oil producing countries. The oil and gas revenue contributes greater percentage of government revenue more than ICT and Nonoil sector especially during oil boom of 1970s before other revenue sectors began to spring up. Some of the sources of petroleum tax revenue includes the petroleum profit tax, oil royalty, oil rent, oil pipeline and license fees, signature bonuses penalty from gas flared, NNPC earnings from direct sales, proceeds from local sales of crude oil to NNPC, proceeds from export sales of crude oil and gas.

Akpokerere and Ekane, (2022) submitted that petroleum income is necessary to carry out basic function of providing the social amenities and infrastructural needs of the people in a market economy such as Nigeria. The justification for revenue generation stems from policy responsibilities, including but are not limited to economic stability, income redistribution, and service delivery in the form of public goods. To meet the fundamental social and infrastructure demands of the populace, the importance of Petroleum resources to the economy of Nigeria cannot be over emphasized. Over 80% of the country's revenue comes from oil and Gas hence the need to explore the derivation, exploration, refining, marketing and all the stakeholders along the Petroleum value chain.

2.1.2 Petroleum Profit Tax

Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) refers to a levy on the firm's profit from oil activities under the Nigerian Petroleum Income Tax Act. It is assessed, levied, and payable on the firms' profits for their engagement in petroleum operations during any accounting period, usually one year (January to December). It is a tax that related to the upstream activities in the oil and gas industry and from petroleum products such Diesel (Automotive Gas Oil), Petrol (Petroleum Motor Spirit), and Household Kerosene (Dual Purpose Kerosene) and it is a source of income to the government. As opined by (Kanu, Ugwu, Ikpor, Nwokoju, & Idume, 2019). The petroleum profit tax was

first introduced in 1959 in Nigeria as the Petroleum Profits Tax Ordinance 1959 with a retrospective effect from 1st January 1958 (Oyeleke *et al.* 2016). The petroleum profit tax in Nigeria is governed by the Petroleum Profits Tax Act, Cap P13 LFN 2004 (as amended). The Act provides for the imposition of Petroleum Profits Tax on the chargeable profits of companies involved in the upstream activities of exploration, drilling, extraction and transportation of crude oil. Companies liable to petroleum profit tax are not liable to Companies Income Tax (CIT) on the same income. The Nigeria's Petroleum Industry Act (PIA) 2021, was a major attempt by government to refit the petroleum sector.

The PIA seeks amongst others to provide legal, governance, regulatory and fiscal framework for the Nigerian Petroleum Industry. Akpan (2021) further stated that activists and host communities have complained that the allocation of 3% to the host community does not give them enough support. In addition, he argued that the levy introduced by Niger Delta Development Commission in addition to the 3% Levy have led to agitations and poor developmental structures had been experience other than Petroleum Profit Tax Act, PPTA (1959) as amended. It is the most significant tax in Nigeria in terms of its share of 95per cent of government revenue and 70per cent of total foreign exchange earnings. The petroleum profit tax are to increase government revenue, generate employment, and regulate the economy and economic activity. Since the oil industry in Nigeria is considered to be the backbone of the economy, in terms of revenue share, PPT is one of Nigeria's largest tax revenues which constitutes over 70% of the aggregate foreign exchange earnings of the government (AbdulRahamoh and Adejare, 2013; Igbasan, 2017; Ojukwu & Odoemelum, 2020).

2.1.3. Crude Oil Export Sales

In Africa, Nigeria is one of the leading producers of crude oil that ranked among the tenth countries that export crude oil globally. Its average daily production of crude oil stands at about 2.2 million barrels per day with most of the oil exploration and production concentrated in the Niger Delta region of the country (OPEC, 2012). Since the oil boom of 1970s, crude oil production had been the main source of foreign exchange earnings and revenue to the Nigerian government. Crude oil is said to have accounted for more than 90% of foreign exchange earnings and accounted for more than 80% of the Federal government revenue (CBN, 2014).

However, the periodic attacks on oil pipelines and production facilities by different militant groups has decreased the volume of oil production (Musa, Saad & Ibrahim, 2017). With the discovery of crude oil in Niger Delta region of Bayelsa at Oloibiri in 1956 by the Shell D'Arcy Petroleum, pioneer production began in 1958 from the company's oil field in Oloibiri in the Eastern Niger Delta. By the late sixties and early seventies, Nigeria had attained a production level of over 2.2 million barrels of crude oil per day and revenue earing's of N166.6 million in 1970 to N 1,591,675.00 million and N6, 530,430.00 million in 2000 and 2008, oil revenue in 2012 was N8025.971 billion and in 2013 and 2014 were N6809.231bn and N5403.51bn, 860.56 billion and 900b respectively in 2023 (NNPCL statistical bulletin, 2024).

Petroleum activities often lead to inflow of foreign resources such as Foreign Direct investment and Portfolio investment. Indeed, the bulk of FDI in majority of the countries that export oil are concentrated in the oil sector. The various channels through which FDI impacts growth and development in the recipient countries have been extensively discussed in the literature, specifically, FDI inflows to developing countries may not help in increasing their stock of capital but may also assist in boosting labour productivity of the host country. Consequently, the level of output, employment creation and potential tax revenues are enhanced in the host countries through crude oil production for local consumption and international earning.

2.1.4. Royalties

Royalty refers to the share of production emanating from lease contract between the right owner of the crude oil or other mineral resources in other words called “lessor” and the “lessee” who is given the right to use the lands for the development of mineral resources. In return for granting the lessee the rights to explore the mineral resources, the lessee gives a share of mineral of any kinds produced or a royalty to the lessor. Royalty Income on the other hand refers to severance taxes or production taxes that are levied directly on the extraction of resources. Royalty income is usually paid on gross revenue and initiated by the first transaction, unless where the buying party poses refinery and eventually both parties accept that the liability could be transferred to the refiner. Royalty is a mandatory payment to the host government based on the volume of production, and is not regarded as tax payment by policymakers (Boadway and Keen, 2014). Royalties are paid on volume of petroleum income extracted in Nigeria (Oremade, 2010). On the other hand, investors participate in royalties through production to the surface, and most of the investors attempt to extend their interest through demand to adjust royalty rates to suit them and warn that any attempt to increase royalty rates may discourage investment (Onifade, 2017).

The royalty rate within onshore is 20% while offshore areas are as follows;

- Areas up to 100m water depth 18.5%
- Areas up to 200m water depth 16.5%
- Areas from 201 to 500m water depth is 12.5%
- Areas from 501 to 800m water depth is 8%
- Areas from 801 to 1000m water depth 4%

2.1.5 Human Development Index

The Human Development Index (HDI) of a country or an economy was introduced by the United Nation Development Programme (UNDP) in 1990 and is a measure that tracks education, health and standard of living of a nation (UNDP, 2019). Nigeria with an HDI of 0.556 in 2022 and 0.559 ranks 140th out of 189 countries and territories around the globe and as such falls within the Medium Human Development category (UNDP, 2019). Human development is an indicator reflecting the welfare of countries as humans are the main factor and the target of a nation development (UNDP, 1990). Human development approach focuses on the human as the development agents (Fukuda-Parr, 2003) since human resources play a central role which determines the national welfare (Manuelli, 2015). Development that focuses on human development is different from economic development within a narrow context that only targets economic development. Instead, human development emphasizes more on the improvement of life quality and freedom for the people (Obianuju & Nworie, 2024). The HDI is a summary measure of average achievements in three key dimensions of human development in the country: a long and healthy life, access to knowledge, and a decent standard of living. HDI provides a composite measure in three dimensions. Namely: (i) longevity and healthy life (life expectancy at birth); (ii) knowledge (adult literacy rate) and average years of schooling for adults (mean years of schooling); and (iii) decent standard of living (purchasing power parity).

Fig 1 Human Development Indices Structure

Source: United Nations Development Programme (2016) ‘Human Development Report 2016’.

The Structure of the Nigerian Petroleum Industry

The Nigerian petroleum industry has the government as a major and dominant actor whose agent is the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). The NNPC, which is charged with the responsibility for monitoring oil exploration, production, research, transportation, refining and marketing of the petroleum products and its derivatives was set up by the NNPC Act of 1977 as the successor agency to the Nigerian National Oil Corporation (NNOC). The Decree 21 by the then president, General Yakubu Gowon in 1971, created the Nigeria National Oil Corporation (NNOC) now NNPC and subsequently NNPC. The NNPC unbundled into different segments such as Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC) and Nigerian Midstream and Downstream Regulatory Commission to manage the country's petroleum industry. Nigeria became the eleventh member country of the OPEC in the same year. Both upstream and downstream activities in the oil industry were delegated to the NUPRC. However, the Ministry of Petroleum Resources was given authority over the regulatory aspects (Udeh, 2021). However, Operational activities of this sector also involve many Joint Venture (JV) agreements and Production sharing Contracts with Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited. The PIA of 2021 mandated the settlor being the International Oil Companies (IOC) to make an annual contribution of 3% of its operational expenditure (OPEX) of the preceding year to the host host community and Nigeria government as the signatory to the account.

They are three major refineries existing in Nigeria with Kaduna Refinery and Petrochemical Company (KRPC), Warri refinery and Petrochemical Ltd (WRPL), Port – Harcourt Refinery and Petrochemical Company (PHRC). Niger Delta stores in its belly gas reserves of commercial quantity, with proven reserves put at 178.5 trillion cubic feet (TCF). It is worth mentioning that the brick of the gas reserves were discovered in the course of oil exploration and production activities. That is to say, that there has to be a deliberate effort to explore gas. The NNPC is presently structured into six functional directorate, namely the corporate services, Refining and Petro-chemical, Commercial and Investments, Finance and Accounts, Exploration and Production as well as Engineering and Technical Services. The FGN regulates the petroleum industry through Ministry of petroleum industry and NNPC.

Fig 2 Oil and Gas Value Chain

Source: Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited & Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission.

2.2 Theoretical Framework Human Capital Theory

The origin of human capital theory goes back to emergence of classical economics in (1776) and thereafter developed a scientific theory. The idea of investing in human capital was first developed by Adam (1776), who argued in the Wealth of Nations that differences between the ways of working of individuals with different levels of education and training reflected differences in the returns necessary to defend the costs of acquiring those skills. Economists such as Elliot (1991) developed the theory of human capital. He is concerned with human capital in terms of the quality, not quantity, of the labour supply. After the manifestation of that concept as a theory, (Dae-bong, 2009) recognized the human capital as one of the important factors of national economic growth in the modern economy. The theory argued that a person’s formal education determines his or her earning power. Human capital theory holds that it is the key competences, skills, knowledge and abilities of the workforce that contributes to organizations competitive advantage. It focuses attention on resourcing, human resource development, and reward strategies and practices.

According to Human Capital Theory, education is an investment because it is believed that it could potentially translate to other areas of human development and social benefits. Human capital theorists believe that education and earning power are correlated, which means, theoretically, that the more education one has, the more one can earn, and that the skills, knowledge and abilities that education provides can be transferred into the work in terms of productivity. According to Tan (2014), the investment of oil resources are not only crucial for individuals but it is also the key to the economic growth and development of a country when measured with HDI. The most valuable of all capital is that invested in human beings”. Adalakun (2011) also described human capital theory that view schooling and training as investment in skills and competence. He argued that based on national expectation or return on investment, individuals make decision on the education and training they receive as a way of augmenting their productivity. The study is specifically anchored on this theory in accordance with Becker (2009) that humans are not just resources but they are capital which produce returns and every expenditure made in order to develop the quality and quantity of capital is an investment activity.

2.3 Empirical Review

Nduokafor, Ovwighose and Nwoye (2024) examined the impact of oil and the non-oil revenue of the Federal Government and how it affects the Economy of Nigeria. The study covered the period of 1981-2023, hence, maximizing the secondary source of data (time series data) collection that were collated from the CBN statistical bulletin and the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) of various years. The results obtained revealed that generally, oil revenue had a negative and non-significant effect on real gross domestic product at ($p > 0.05$) of Nigeria during the period. On the other hand, it was discovered that the non-oil revenue and the allocation from federation account both had a positive and significant effect on real gross domestic product at ($p < 0.05$). The study concluded that proper allocation and judicious use of these funds can stimulate economic activities at various levels of government, enhance infrastructure development, ensure a safer business environment and improve public services. In a related study, Dauda, Musa Alege, Philip (2023), analyzed a study on Oil revenue and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria. The study explored the nexus between the generated oil revenue in Nigeria from 1981 to 2021 and its possible influences on the relative growth of the economy on a sustainable basis. Utilizing the Johansen Co-Integration test, Granger Causality Technique as well as the Error Corrections Method (ECM) to analyze the sourced data from both the World Development Indicators and the Nigeria Central Bank, the findings indicated that decline in oil revenue resulted to a decrease in economic growth (GDP). This study, therefore, recommends the formulation and efficient implementation of policies that facilitate prudent identification and collection, the utilization of the generated oil income and its deployment to critical, underdeveloped and developing sectors of the economy. In the same vein, Nnah (2023) carried a study to investigate the impact of petroleum revenue on public spending in Nigeria with exchange rate as a moderating variable. The findings of the study revealed that petroleum profit tax has a positive significant effect on capital spending in Nigeria; oil proceed has a positive but insignificant effect on capital spending in Nigeria; oil royalty has a positive insignificant effect on capital spending in Nigeria; concessional rental has a negative but significant effect on capital spending; oil proceeds has a negative significant effect on recurrent spending in Nigeria. Based on the above, it was recommended among others that the government should encourage more private company participation so that better equipped refineries can be built and the cost of refining crude oil will reduce; more so security should be boosted on the high sea where crude oil products are being smuggled. This will help reduce the loss from illegal export of crude oil products. On the other hand, Olayungbo, (2019) studied the impact of oil income on Nigeria's economic growth from 1970 to 2015 using the Bayesian time-varying parameters as analytical tools. The findings reveal that the Nigeria's economy grew greatly and favorably throughout the period under consideration due to the utilization oil revenue.

Salisu and Azare (2020) examined the short and the long-run effects of oil and gas revenue and control of corruption on economic performance in Nigeria. Auto Regressive Distributed Lags (ARDL) was used in achieving the objective of the study. The short-run model reveals that economic performance is significantly explained by the lags of oil and gas revenue, and control of corruption. However, the long-run model coefficients produced result that is contrary to the a priori expectation, though they are statistically insignificant. This indicated that, oil and gas revenue, and control of corruption promotes economic growth in the short-run and reduces it in long run. The research therefore recommends anticorruption policy of establishing a special court attach to anticorruption agencies in order to mitigate corrupt practices and subsequently improve the standard of living in Nigeria.

From the above related works (Asagunla and Agbede, 2018; Obaretin *et al.*, 2019; Nweze and Edame, 2016; Olayungbo, 2019; Olayungbo and Adediran, 2017) all reported a positive and long-run association between oil

revenue and economic growth in Nigeria while others such as (Akinleye *et al.*, 2021; Ebimobowei, 2022; Omitogun *et al.*, 2018) reported a contrary association between revenue generated from crude oil transaction and growth in the economy. The overall findings from these studies are the outcomes with inconsistency including contradictory findings with economic growth and development using RGDP or GDP or liner regression method like Akinlolu Agbara Olojede and Nejo Femi Michael (2020). In affirmation of other studies this present study reflect the PIA of 2021 that accommodates other players and extension of more variables of petroleum income using the parameter of HDI as dependent variable for a period of (2005-2023).

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research design employed in this study utilizes an *ex-post facto* which allows historical data from past events. Ex-post facto research design was deemed appropriate because the events under study already took place and the variables cannot therefore be manipulated (Nworie, Okafor & John-Akamelu, 2022). This study used secondary data in form of an annual time series data from 2005 - 2023, covering a period of 19 years. The choice of using 2005 was as result official report of UNDP in Nigeria.

The nature and source of the data that the researcher used were secondary sources which were obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin of various years, Nigeria Bureau of Statistics and Nigerian National Petroleum Company Limited (NNPCL) yearly report, NEITI, Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and other relevant databases while HDI with three major indices are sourced from World Development Indicators and UNDP. HDI was conceived using three basic dimensions and they are;

1. Longevity (long and healthy life)
2. Education (knowledge)
3. Living standards (a decent standard of living)

Petroleum income: This is the total amount of income derived from the sales of crude oil/refined petroleum products annually in the country both internally and internationally in local currency unit (Naira).

Following the work of Akinlo (2012) in assessing the importance of oil revenue in the development of the Nigerian economy over the period of 1960-2009. The adapted form of the model is expressed below

$$GDP_t = F(GDP_{t-1}, OREV_t, GEXP_t) \dots \dots \dots Eq(1)$$

Where;

GDP is the Gross Domestic Product

GDP_t = lagged form of GDP

OREV = Oil Revenue

OILP = Oil Production

Where GDP = Gross Domestic Product OREV = Oil Revenue GEXP = Government

Expenditure μ is the stochastic term.

Modifying equation (i), this study adopted the model below;

$$HDI = f(COIL, PPT, RI) \dots \dots \dots Eq (iii)$$

The linear form of the equation (iii) is expressed in econometric form with error term as:

$$HDI = \Omega_0 + \Omega_1 COIL + \Omega_2 PPT + \Omega_3 RI + \mu$$

Where;

HDI = Human Development Index

COIL = Crude export income

PPT = Petroleum Profit Tax

RI= Royalty Income

Ω_0 = constant intercept

Ω_0 - Ω_3 = slope of coefficients of the explanatory variables captured in the model, U_i = stochastic disturbance term. This study employed Multiple Regression Method of OLS to examine the effect of Petroleum income on Human Development Index between the period of 2005 and 2023. The Unit root test was carried to determine the statistical properties of the variables and to determine if they are stationarity, this is done in order to avoid spurious regression and misleading judgment. The co-integration test and Descriptive statistics were employed to examine whether the variables exhibit both the short and long run impact within the variables in the model using *eview version 12* software.

Decision Rule 1: Accept the alternate hypothesis and reject the null hypothesis if the Pvalue is less than the chosen level of significance (0.05). It implies that the estimated variable has significant impact on the dependent variable.

Decision Rule 2: Accept the null hypothesis and reject the alternate hypothesis if the Pvalue is greater than the chosen level of significance (0.05). It implies that the estimated variable has non-significant impact on the dependent variable.

4.0 RESULTS

The following variables were used in the study; these include human development index (LOGHDI), crude export income (LOGCOIL), petroleum profit tax (LOGPPT) and Royalty Income (LOGRI). The descriptive analysis was done using the raw data whereas the inferential analysis (including regression analysis) was done using the natural logarithmic transformation of each of the variables.

4.1.1 Descriptive Analysis

Table 4.1 Descriptive Analysis

	Human Development Index	Crude Oil Export Income (\$'b)	Petroleum Profit Tax (\$'b)	Royalty Income (₦'b)
Mean	0.635105	9563.447	11831362	57084.82
Median	0.466000	8184.481	11177366	4111.640
Maximum	1.564000	27536.30	20968131	356823.0
Minimum	0.357000	1076.765	2011156.	421.5000
Std. Dev.	0.383847	5781.924	5431944.	125777.5
Skewness	1.870014	1.412295	-0.070075	1.879916
Kurtosis	4.667878	6.060245	2.153201	4.553315
Jarque-Bera	13.27596	13.73020	0.583229	13.10139
Probability	0.001310	0.001044	0.747057	0.001429
Sum	12.06700	181705.5	2.25E+08	1084612.
Sum Sq. Dev.	2.652092	6.02E+08	5.31E+14	2.85E+11
Observations	19	19	19	19

Source: Researcher computation from E-View 12.

The Human Development Index (HDI) in Nigeria, as shown in Table 4.1, has a mean value of 0.635, suggesting a moderate level of human development on average over the study period.

However, the median is 0.466, which is significantly lower than the mean, indicating that the distribution is right-skewed, with several years of much higher HDI values pulling the average upward. This skewness is confirmed by the positive skewness coefficient of 1.87, reflecting a long tail to the right. The standard deviation of 0.384 shows a relatively high level of dispersion in HDI values, signifying substantial variations in human development over time. The minimum value is 0.357 and the maximum is 1.564, showing a wide range, with the maximum even exceeding 1 (which typically suggests a calculation anomaly or composite index transformation). The kurtosis value of 4.67 indicates a leptokurtic distribution, meaning the HDI data is peaked with fat tails, possibly due to extreme values. The Jarque-Bera statistic of 13.28 and its associated p-value of 0.00131 reject the null hypothesis of normality, confirming the distribution is significantly non-normal.

Regarding Crude Oil Export Income, the mean value is \$9.56 billion, while the median is \$8.18 billion, suggesting a positively skewed distribution where some very high-income years have elevated the average. This skewness is supported by a skewness coefficient of 1.41, indicating a longer right tail. The standard deviation is \$5.78 billion, showing high variability in oil export earnings. The maximum income was \$27.54 billion, with a minimum of \$1.08 billion, reflecting considerable fluctuation in earnings from oil exports. The kurtosis value of 6.06 confirms a leptokurtic distribution with potential outliers or extreme income years. Again, the Jarque-Bera statistic (13.73) and low p-value (0.00104) suggest the data is not normally distributed.

For Petroleum Profit Tax, the mean value is \$11.83 billion, and the median is slightly lower at \$11.18 billion, indicating a nearly symmetric distribution. This is reinforced by a very low skewness of -0.07, close to zero. The standard deviation is \$5.43 billion, suggesting notable variability in tax revenue, with a minimum of \$2.01 billion and a maximum of \$20.97 billion. The kurtosis value of 2.15 is close to the normal distribution's benchmark of 3, suggesting a mesokurtic (moderately peaked) distribution. The Jarque-Bera test statistic of 0.58 with a pvalue of 0.7471 indicates that the distribution does not significantly differ from normality, making this variable the most normally distributed among the four.

Lastly, for Royalty Income, measured in Nigerian Naira (₦), the mean is ₦57,084.82 million, while the median is ₦4,111.64 million, revealing a highly skewed distribution where a few very high-income years skew the average upward. This is strongly supported by the high skewness value of 1.88. The data exhibits extreme variation with a standard deviation of ₦125,777.5 million, a minimum value of ₦421.5 million, and a maximum of ₦356,823 million. The kurtosis of 4.55 indicates a peaked distribution with heavy tails. As with HDI and crude oil export income, the Jarque-Bera statistic (13.10) and p-value (0.00143) reject normality, confirming the presence of significant outliers or non-normal behavior in royalty revenues.

4.2. Unit Root Test

The results presented in Table 2 are from the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test, which assesses the stationarity of the variables. A variable is considered stationary if its statistical properties like mean and variance do not change over time, which is crucial for time series analysis (Nwoye, Udunwoke & Nworie, 2023).

Table 2: Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit

Variable	T-stat	5% Critical Value	P-value	Remark
LOGHDI	-5.505508	-3.052169	0.0004	I(0)
LOGPPT	-3.700965	-3.040391	0.0137	I(0)
LOGCOIL	-3.759122	-3.052169	0.0129	I(0)

LOGRI	-4.424695	-3.052169	0.0035	I(0)
-------	-----------	-----------	--------	------

Source: Output of E-view 12

As shown in Table 4.2 above, all four variables—LOGHDI, LOGPPT, LOGCOIL, and LOGRI—have test statistics (T-stat) more negative than the 5% critical value and p-values less than 0.05, indicating that the null hypothesis of a unit root can be rejected. Therefore, all variables are stationary at level, denoted as I(0). This implies that the data do not require differencing and are suitable for time series modeling in their current form.

Given that all variables are stationary at level, the use of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) is appropriate for this study. OLS regression assumes that the variables involved are stationary to avoid spurious relationships. Non-stationary variables could produce misleading statistical inferences. Since the ADF test confirms stationarity, OLS can yield consistent and unbiased estimators. The essence of the ADF test in this context is to ensure the validity of further econometric modeling by confirming that the variables are suitable for regression analysis without the need for transformations or corrections for non-stationarity.

4.3. Analyses Results

4.3.1. Multiple Regression Analysis for study

The outcome of the multiple regression analysis is as presented in table 4.3 below

Table 4.3 Regression Analysis

Dependent Variable: LOGHDI

Method: Least Squares

Date: 05/14/25 Time: 04:31

Sample: 2005 2023

Included observations: 19

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOGCOIL	0.029940	0.019814	1.511081	0.1515
LOGPPT	-0.073757	0.032787	-2.249618	0.0399
LOGRI	-0.054829	0.009414	5.824146	0.0000
C	0.905221	0.202503	4.470161	0.0004
R-squared	0.897357	Mean dependent var		0.300903
Adjusted R-squared	0.876828	S.D. dependent var		0.071809
S.E. of regression	0.025202	Akaike info criterion		-4.339128
Sum squared resid	0.009527	Schwarz criterion		-4.140299
Log likelihood	45.22172	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-4.305478
F-statistic	43.71250	Durbin-Watson stat		1.566068
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Researcher computation from E -View 12

The regression results presented in Table 4.3 show that the model explaining the effect of crude oil revenue components on human development index (LOGHDI) is statistically valid and robust. The Adjusted R-squared value of 0.8768 suggests that approximately 87.7% of the variations in LOGHDI are jointly explained by the

three independent variables: LOGPPT (Petroleum Profit Tax), LOGRI (Royalties Income), and LOGCOIL (Crude Oil Export

Income). This high explanatory power indicates that the model is well-fitted to the data. Furthermore, the F-statistic has a p-value of 0.000000, which is less than the 0.05 significance level. This implies that the overall model is statistically significant, meaning that at least one of the independent variables significantly affects LOGHDI.

The Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.566 is slightly below the ideal value of 2, suggesting mild positive autocorrelation in the residuals. While not severe, this should be monitored in extended analysis. Regarding the constant term ($C = 0.9052$, $p = 0.0004$), it is statistically significant at the 5% level. The constant represents the expected value of LOGHDI when all the predictors are zero, and in this context, it serves as the baseline level of human development in the absence of oil-derived revenues.

4.2. Test of Hypotheses

The decision rule is as follows:

Accept null hypothesis (H_0) if p-value of the t-statistics is greater than 0.05 reject null hypothesis (H_0) if p-value of the t-statistics is less than 0.05

4.2.1 Testing of Hypothesis 1

H0₁: Crude oil export income has no significant impact on Human Development Index development in Nigeria. The coefficient of LOGCOIL is 0.0299 ($p = 0.1515$), suggesting a 1% increase in Crude Oil Export Income results in a 0.0299% increase in HDI. This marginal effect is positive, indicating a theoretically beneficial link between crude oil export earnings and human development. However, this effect is not statistically significant at the 5% level, since the p-value exceeds 0.05. As a result, we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_{01}) and conclude that Crude oil export income has a positive but statistically non-significant effect on human development in Nigeria ($\beta = 0.0299$, $p = 0.1515$).

4.2.2 Testing of Hypothesis 2

H0₂: Petroleum profit tax has no significant impact on Human Development in Nigeria

The coefficient for LOGPPT is -0.0738 ($p = 0.0399$). This implies that a 1% increase in Petroleum Profit Tax is associated with a 0.0738% decrease in the Human Development Index (HDI), holding other variables constant. The marginal effect is negative, suggesting that increased government revenue from petroleum profits may not be effectively translated into human development gains. This may be due to inefficiencies, leakages, or misallocation in how such revenue is used. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, we reject the null hypothesis (H_{02}) and conclude that Petroleum Profit Tax has a statistically significant effect on HDI at the 5% level, albeit a negative one. Hence, Petroleum profit tax exerts a negative and significant effect on human development ($\beta = -0.0738$, $p = 0.0399$).

4.2.3. Testing of Hypothesis 3

H0₂: Royalties Income has no significant impact on Human Development in Nigeria

The coefficient for LOGRI is -0.0548 ($p = 0.0000$). This indicates that a 1% increase in Royalties Income leads to a 0.0548% decrease in HDI, all else being equal. The marginal effect is again negative and significant, pointing to a paradox where increased royalties from oil resources may correspond with declining human development. This could reflect underlying structural issues, such as poor governance or inequitable distribution of oil revenues. Given that the p-value is far below 0.05, the effect is highly significant, and we therefore reject the null hypothesis

(H03). We conclude that Royalties income has a negative and significant effect on human development in Nigeria ($\beta = -0.0548$, $p = 0.0000$).

4.4. Discussion of Findings

The finding that crude oil export income has a positive but statistically non-significant effect on human development in Nigeria indicates that while oil exports may contribute financially to the national economy, their direct impact on citizens' well-being—measured by health, education, and income—remains unclear or weak. This could be due to a disconnection between revenue generation and resource allocation in sectors that directly influence human development. Often, export income is absorbed into general government revenue without targeted mechanisms ensuring its investment in public goods. Issues such as corruption, administrative inefficiencies, and the prioritization of macroeconomic objectives over social welfare may explain why the gains from oil exports do not automatically improve human development outcomes. This finding aligns with the work of Nduokafor, Ovwighose and Nwoye (2024), who also found that oil revenue had a negative and statistically non-significant effect on real GDP in Nigeria, emphasizing the ineffective transmission of oil income into development outcomes. Similarly, Salisu and Azare (2020) highlighted that while oil and gas revenue may have short-run benefits, its long-run effects are insignificant, reinforcing the possibility that oil wealth is not being channeled into sustainable development. However, contrasting evidence exists in Dauda, Musa Alege, and Philip (2023), who reported that a decline in oil revenue leads to a decline in economic growth, suggesting some level of dependence on oil income. Further supporting this is Olayungbo (2019), who found that oil income contributed positively to economic growth during the studied period. Nonetheless, these differences may arise from the use of different indicators—GDP versus HDI—and support the notion that economic growth does not necessarily translate into human development.

The finding that petroleum profit tax exerts a negative and significant effect on human development in Nigeria is both revealing and concerning. This suggests that as the government collects more taxes from petroleum-related profits, there may be a corresponding decline in measurable human development outcomes. One possible explanation is the misallocation or misappropriation of tax revenue, where funds are not directed toward education, healthcare, or social infrastructure. Additionally, the tax burden on petroleum firms may indirectly affect employment levels, local investment, or resource reinvestment in communities, particularly if tax policy discourages operational expansion or leads to capital flight. In comparison with existing literature, this result partially contradicts Nnah (2023) who found that petroleum profit tax had a positive significant effect on capital spending, indicating that, at least in terms of government investment, the tax was being directed toward development purposes. However, this does not guarantee an improvement in human development, particularly if such capital spending is inefficient or does not reach vulnerable populations. The negative implication in this study is consistent with broader concerns highlighted by Salisu and Azare (2020) regarding the long-run inefficiency of oil-derived income in improving economic or social outcomes. Similarly, Akinleye et al. (2021) and Ebimobowei (2022) reported a negative relationship between oil revenue and development indicators, adding weight to the argument that petroleum revenue—particularly tax-based—may not be strategically invested for societal benefit. These contrasting findings underscore the importance of differentiating between government capital spending and its actual impact on HDI.

The finding that royalty's income has a negative and significant effect on human development indicates that increasing revenue from oil royalties does not support and may even hinder progress in health, education, and living standards in Nigeria. Royalties are meant to compensate the state for the extraction of natural resources,

but this revenue stream appears to have a detrimental link with human development. This may reflect governance failures, particularly in the equitable redistribution of such funds. Resource-rich communities often suffer from environmental degradation, displacement, and lack of access to basic services, despite being sources of massive royalty payments. When royalties are not transparently allocated or are mismanaged, the result is underdevelopment in critical areas of human welfare. This outcome agrees with Nnah (2023), who found that oil royalty had a positive but insignificant effect on capital spending, implying a limited or weak developmental role. Nduokafor et al. (2024) also support the broader idea that oil-derived income, including royalties, does not significantly enhance economic indicators like GDP, which often precedes improvements in HDI. Additionally, Salisu and Azare (2020) point out the long-run inefficiency of oil revenue on economic performance, further supporting the idea that royalties do not promote sustainable human development. Yet, this finding stands in contrast with the optimism in Olayungbo and Adediran (2017) and Dauda et al. (2023), who see oil revenues as having a generally positive impact. These contradictions may stem from different dependent variables and contextual nuances, but the current study's focus on HDI as a measure of human welfare rather than economic output brings to light the depth of the disconnect between oil wealth and human-centered development.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS 5.1 Conclusion

The findings from the study on the impact of petroleum income on human development in Nigeria between 2005 and 2023 reveal a complex and somewhat paradoxical relationship between oil-derived revenues and development outcomes. The presence of both negative and non-significant effects suggests that the substantial financial gains from petroleum may not be effectively transforming into tangible improvements in human well-being. This could point to systemic inefficiencies, where institutional, governance, or structural barriers hinder the translation of resource wealth into developmental progress. It highlights the disconnect between national revenue generation and improvements in the Human Development Index (HDI), which reflects education, health, and income dimensions.

Moreover, the significant negative effects observed in components such as petroleum profit tax and royalties income indicate that increasing fiscal extraction from the oil sector does not necessarily correlate with better human development metrics. These patterns may reflect challenges in public financial management, where increased revenue might be absorbed into non-productive expenditures or lost to leakages. Instead of supporting social services or infrastructure, the revenues may be channeled into areas that do not directly impact the everyday quality of life of the population. The implications extend to how revenue mobilization strategies from natural resources can unintentionally deepen inequalities or neglect social investment priorities. Therefore, petroleum income, while economically substantial, does not guarantee developmental outcomes in contexts where governance and resource allocation frameworks may be weak or misaligned with developmental goals. The disconnect between resource inflow and HDI performance raises concerns about long-term sustainability and inclusiveness of growth in resource-rich economies.

5.2. Recommendations

The following recommendations were made by the researcher;

- 1. To the Ministry of Budget and National Planning:** Given the positive but statistically nonsignificant effect of crude oil export income on human development, the Ministry should develop and implement a strategic framework that explicitly links crude oil export earnings to investments in education, healthcare, and infrastructure. This would ensure that oil revenue translates into long-term human development outcomes rather than being absorbed into general expenditures.

2. To the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the Office of the Accountant General of the Federation: In light of the significant negative effect of petroleum profit tax on human development, these agencies should jointly audit and evaluate how petroleum tax revenues are allocated and spent. A performance-based budgeting system should be adopted to ensure that funds generated from petroleum taxes are directed toward development-focused projects that benefit the wider population.

3. To the Nigerian Upstream Petroleum Regulatory Commission (NUPRC): Given the significant negative effect of royalties income on human development, the Commission should establish a mandatory development fund sourced from royalty payments. This fund should be transparently managed and strictly allocated to human development priorities in oil-producing communities, including healthcare delivery, educational support, and livelihood enhancement programs.

References

- Abdul-Rahamoh, F.H., Adejare, A.T. (2013), Analysis of the effect of petroleum profit tax on Nigerian economy. *Asian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 1(1), 1-12.
- Akinlo, A.E. (2012) 'How Important is Oil in Nigeria's Economic Growth?' *Journal of Sustainable Development* 5(World Bank (Last updated 2014) 'The World Bank: Data: Merchandize Export (Total Merchandize), Nigeria'.
- Akintayo, O. (2022). Oil exports account for 80% total national revenue. *The Punch*.
- Akpokerere, O.E & Ekane, R.O (2022). Oil and non-oil revenue and the Nigerian economy. *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*. 4, (11) 441-457.
- Appah, E. (2022). Oil revenue and economic growth of Nigeria: 1990 – 2019. *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* 5(1) 17-46)
- Bassey, B. E., Ahaneku, R. N., Ogar, E. A., Usen, G. E., & Ubi, J. J. (2020). Effect of Green Accounting on the Performance of Oil and Gas Companies in Nigeria. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 1(4) 67-89
- Becker, G. (2009). *Human Capital: A Theoretical and Empirical Analysis, With Specialized Reference to Education*. The University of Chicago.
- Cawood, F.T. (2007). An independent analysis of the 2006 draft royalty bill for the South African mineral and petroleum sectors. *Journal of the Southern African Institute of Mining and Metallurgy*, 107 (8),493-503.
- Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical bulletin, (2020).Revenue allocations to the three tiers of government plus derivation.
- Dauda, M.A., Philip. (2023). Oil revenue and sustainable economic growth in Nigeria: empirical analysis. In: *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy* 13 (4), S. 150 - 155.

Ebimobowei, A. (2022). Oil revenue and economic growth of Nigeria: 1990–2019. *African Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(1), 17-46.

Ebo (2019) a critical Evaluation of Implications of Oil Revenue for Nigeria Economic Growth *Continental Journal of Social Sciences* 11 (1): 17 – 28

Kanu .C, Idume G, Nwokeiwu, J Ugwu, J Ikpor, I, M., & Edeogu, P., N. (2019) Impact of the Petroleum Products Prices on Consumer Products Prices in Nigeria, *International Journal of Mechanical Engineering and Technology*, 10(10), . 249-262.

National Bureau of Statistics. (2020), *Gross Domestic Product First Quarter 2020 (Advance Estimate)*. United States: Bureau of Economic Analysis